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Low-cost, High Strength Polyacrylonitrile Precursor Fibre

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Carbon Fibre Value Chain

Development and properties of precursor fibre

TG/CF PAN blend solutions

Flow-sweep behavior of TG, CF and TG/CF PAN

TG, CF and TG70/CF30 precursor fibres (from left to right)

SEM image of cross-section of precursor fibre

Mechanical properties of precursor fibres

